

Azadirachtins — Supermolecules for Insect Control†

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The medicinal uses of various parts of the neem tree (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) have been known in the Indian System of Medicine (Ayurveda) for over 2000 years. Aqueous extracts of powdered neem kernels have been used by Indian farmers for control of insect pests for centuries, although this practice was given up with the advent of powerful synthetic pesticides. It was only in the 1960s that the harmful effects of these toxic substances on the ecosystem was realised and the quest for more benign pest control agents began. There was hope that the plant kingdom could offer a solution since plants have been defending themselves from insects and pathogenic fungi for millions of years.

At this time (early 1960s) several reports appeared in India on the ability of neem kernel extract to deter feeding by insects on plants and the traditional use of such extracts in India for insect control was recalled. Pradhan *et al.*¹ and Sinha and Gulati² reported 100% antifeedant effect on *Schistocerca gregaria* and *Schistocerca migratoria* by use of neem kernel extract. The German entomologist Schmutterer had also observed on a visit to Africa that after an invasion by locusts only the neem trees survived. Prompted by these reports Butterworth and Morgan^{3,4} undertook a chemical examination of neem kernel extract and by bioactivity-guided chromatographic fractionation isolated a compound which was named azadirachtin with astonishing activity against insects. The compound inhibited feeding by the desert locust totally at a concentration of 40 $\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$. This discovery generated an explosive interest in the West, not only in chemists but also in entomologists. Since 1967, over a hundred compounds have been isolated from various parts of the neem tree⁵⁻⁸ and many other plants of the family Meliaceae were investigated mostly by scientists in the West. Morgan's report caused a second renaissance in the study of plant products.

The most interesting compounds from neem are from the kernels and the well characterised compounds are the triterpenoids which all seem to be derived from the triterpene tirucallol, as can be inferred from the stereochemical arrangements of the methyl groups at C-10, C-13, C-14 and the side-chain at C-17. The compounds occurring in neem arise presumably by successive rearrangements and oxidation of the plant triterpenes and fall into different groups. There are a few triterpenoids in which the side-chain is intact as in

meliantriol. There are a large number in which four carbon atoms C-24 to C-27 have been cleaved from side-chain leading to tetranortriterpenoids. Of these, those with the remaining side-chain carbons cyclised to a furan ring are termed limonoids (meliacins) of which there are over thirty, a typical member being azadirone.

The most important of the constituents of neem kernels are the *C-seco*-tetranortriterpenoids which are distinct from the limonoids. The first member of this group is the azadirachtin isolated by Butterworth and Morgan^{3,4}. Subsequently, in an article contributed to a monograph⁹, Rembold reported that by submitting neem kernel extract to preparative hplc, besides Morgan's azadirachtin (termed A) and Kraus's 3-tigloylazadirachtol (termed B), other analogues which were named azadirachtins, C, D, E, F and G were obtained. No structure could be assigned to C, but structures were assigned to the others on the basis of nmr spectra. Unfortunately, neither the experimental work nor spectra have been published so far to the best of our knowledge.

The criterion for classification as an azadirachtin should be the presence of two segments, one a 1,3-dioxygenated decalin system and the other a dihydrofuran (or modified) system, which are connected by a single bond between C-8 and C-14, there being no other bond connecting the two halves. There are at present thirty compounds belonging to this class isolated from natural sources. In this article we would like to present a brief review of the structures of the azadirachtins. We adopt Kraus's proposal of dividing this group into azadirachtins, azadirachtols and meliacarpins⁸ to avoid further confusion which exists in the naming of compounds from neem.

Azadirachtin (1) :

Isolation : This compound was first isolated by Butterworth and Morgan in 1967^{3,4}. Following the discovery of its potent activity as an insect antifeedant and growth regulator, large quantities were needed for structural and entomological studies. The isolation procedure reported by Uebel *et al.*¹⁰ yielded 8.7 g of azadirachtin from 48.2 kg of neem kernels and that of Yamasaki *et al.*¹¹, 56 mg from 1 kg of neem seeds. The most cited paper for the isolation of azadirachtin is that by Schroeder and Nakanishi¹² which is lengthy with many steps, although 3 g was obtained from 2 kg of neem kernels.

†Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on his 75th. birth anniversary.

	R	R ¹
1	Tigloyl	Ac
3	H	Ac
4	Tigloyl	H
5	Dihydrotigloyl	Ac
6	Tigloyl	E-Cinnamoyl
7	Isobutyryl	Ac
8	Isovaleryl	Ac
9	Isocaproyl	
15	H	Tigloyl

A convenient procedure for isolation of pure azadirachtin from neem kernel extract using direct preparative hplc was reported from our laboratory^{13,14}. When neem kernel extract free from water-soluble material was subjected to preparative hplc (RP₁₈ column, 30 mm) using methanol-water (60 : 40) as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 15 ml min⁻¹, a number of peaks (1-5) separated. After 40 min the mobile phase was changed to methanol-water (70 : 30) and the flow rate to 20 ml min⁻¹, when peaks 6-13 were eluted (Fig. 1). When peak 2 was submitted to a second preparative hplc on a reverse phase column using acetonitrile-water (28 : 72) it was resolved into three peaks (Fig. 2), and material recovered from the middle peak was azadirachtin

Fig. 1. Chromatogram of neem kernel constituents (preparative RP-18 column, 25×3 cm ID).

Fig. 2. Chromatogram of azadirachtins A, D and K : (1) azadirachtin, (2) azadirachtin A, (3) azadirachtin K.

(>96% pure) which could be easily crystallised from ethyl acetate-hexane.

	R	R ¹
10	OMe	H
11	H	OMe

Azadirachtin has been tested against 600 or more species of insects in which it is effective as antifeedant at a concentration of 10–100 ppm and as a growth regulator at 1–10 ppm.

	R ₁	R ₂
12	OH	H
13	H	OH
14	H	OAc

Structure elucidation : The elucidation of structure of azadirachtin proved a difficult job and took nearly eighteen years, some wrong structures being proposed before the final correct structure was reached. Several laboratories were engaged in this task, which has been admirably summarised in a series of four papers in a Tetrahedron Symposium^{15–18}. Kraus's group was the first to propose the correct structure, which was confirmed by X-ray crystallographic analysis on

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detigloyl-22,23-dihydroazadirachtin (DTA)¹⁹ since azadirachtin itself could not be crystallised. Subsequently, azadirachtin was obtained in crystalline form in our laboratory and the structure was determined by X-ray diffraction studies, which fully confirmed the structure arrived at from nmr data^{20,21}. However, the conformations of the structures derived by X-ray studies for azadirachtin and DTA were distinctly different. In the former there is no intramolecular hydrogen bonding between the C-11 hydroxy and the epoxy oxygen in the other segment, but only with the carbonyl of the carbomethoxy on C-11. In DTA, the two segments are linked by a hydrogen bond between the C-11 hydroxy and the epoxy oxygen on the other segment. The doubling of nmr signals at low temperatures in azadirachtin is certainly not due to any intramolecular hydrogen bond between the two segments. It is probably due to atropoisomerism, brought about by restriction of rotation about the C8–C14 bond at low temperatures.

3-Tigloylazadirachtol (azadirachtin-B) (19) :

Isolation : This compound was first isolated by Klenk *et al.*²² by conventional column chromatography and Rembold *et al.*^{23,24} and structure determined from nmr data. It was also isolated later by Govindachari *et al.*¹⁴ by direct preparative hplc as discussed earlier. When peak 3 (Fig. 1) material was subjected to a second preparative hplc using an RP-18 column and acetonitrile-water (28 : 72) as eluent, a purer material was obtained. This could not be crystallised and was further purified using the recycling mode²⁵. This material readily crystallised and would be used for structure determination by X-ray crystallography. The placement of the tigloyl group at C-3 is based entirely on NOE studies and it would be desirable to have independent confirmation.

	R	R ¹	R ²	R ³
18	Tigloyl	Ac	OH	H
22	H	Tigloyl	H	OH

	R	R ¹
19	H	Tigloyl
20	H	2',3'-Dihydrotigloyl
21	H	Isobutyryl
23	Tigloyl	Ac
24	H	Ac
25	H	H

1-Tigloyl-3-acetyl-11-hydroxymeliacarpin (azadirachtin-D) (26) :

Isolation : This compound was first isolated by Rembold^{9,26} without furnishing any experimental details of isolation and without spectral data and later by Kraus *et al.*²⁷ and Rojatar and Nagasampagi²⁸. During the second hplc process of peak 2 (Fig. 1), this compound preceded azadirachtin (Fig. 2), and was subjected to a third hplc using the recycling mode yielding pure azadirachtin D, m.p. 196°. Rojatar and Nagasampagi²⁸ obtained it as a gum.

11-Demethoxycarbonylazadirachtin (azadirachtin-H). 11 α -H and 11 β -H epimers, 12 and 13 :

In a symposium abstract Nagasampagi *et al.*²⁹ depicted a structure corresponding to the 11 α -H epimer with no details. As a follow-up in the full paper published by them in 1994 only ¹H nmr data was provided on the 11 α -H epimer without any isolation details or characterisation³⁰. ¹H and ¹³C nmr data were given for the 11 β -H epimer. Only 3 mg was obtained from 20 kg of neem kernels. In our work using direct preparative hplc, when peak 1, in Fig. 1 was put through a second preparative hplc using acetonitrile-water (28 : 72) it split into two peaks from one of which the 11 α -H epimer was obtained, the other being azadirachtin I (Fig. 3). In both these compounds the C11-H was α , since the nmr peaks for 11-H were doublets (*J* 4.4 Hz) due to coupling with 9-H^{14,31}. Both the compounds were crystalline.

Fig. 3. Chromatogram of azadirachtins H and I : (1) azadirachtin I, (2) azadirachtin H.

With other batches of neem kernels extracted at a later time, only the 11β-H epimer was isolated and the 11β-H was a singlet³². Ramji *et al.*³³ also reported the isolation of the 11β-H epimer but all physical data are at variance with our values obtained on crystalline material. It has been found that both 11α-H and 11β-H epimers occur in the kernels, some batches of kernels giving the 11α-H epimer but in a large number of cases the 11β-H epimer. In the same batch of kernels either the 11α-H or 11β-H epimer is obtained but never both together. It was also found that the 11α-H epimer in CDCl₃ solution was transformed rapidly by addition of a drop of D₂O to the 11β-H epimer³⁴. The structure of the 11β-H epimer has been confirmed by X-ray crystallography³⁵.

	R	R ¹	R ²	R ³
26	Tigloyl	Ac	OH	COOMe
27	Tigloyl	Ac	OH	H
28	Tigloyl	Ac	=O	
30	H	Tigloyl	H	COOMe

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1-Tigloyl-3-acetyl-11-hydroxy-11-demethoxycarbonylmeliacarpin (azadirachtin I) (27) :

The chemistry is similar to that of azadirachtin H which has been studied in greater detail^{14,31}. It differs from azadirachtin H in having a methyl group in place of the carbomethoxy at C-4 and is classified as a meliacarpin.

11-Dehydroxy-11-oxo-azadirachtin-11,12-lactone (azadirachtin K) (17) :

As mentioned earlier, peak 2 (Fig. 1) was resolved into essentially azadirachtin-A and azadirachtin-D by a second preparative hplc using acetonitrile-water (28 : 72). There was also a small third peak which on work-up yielded the six-membered lactone, which was termed as azadirachtin K³⁶.

13,14-Desepoxyazadirachtin A (18) :

13,14-Desepoxyazadirachtin A was isolated from one of the peaks in Fig. 1 following that of azadirachtin B. The structure was determined by detailed nmr analysis³⁷.

3α-Acetoxy-1α-hydroxyazadirachtol (24) :

This compound was isolated from the hplc peak preceding that of azadirachtin H and I as a crystalline solid, m.p. 132–135³⁸. The same compound has been reported by Nagasampagi and Rojatar as a gummy liquid isolated by column chromatography³⁹.

Azadirachtol (25) :

This compound was obtained earlier by removal of the tigloyl group in azadirachtin-B^{40,9,26}. It has now been isolated from kernel extract from a peak preceding the azadirachtins H and I peaks (Fig. 1). The structure was determined from nmr data³⁸.

3-Tigloylmeliacarpin (30) :

When the total triterpenoids from neem oil was subjected to preparative hplc, it gave essentially the same type of peaks as for the material from the kernel extract^{41,42}. On submitting the peak containing azadirachtin A and azadirachtin D to a second preparative hplc with acetonitrile-water (28 : 72), a new peak appeared before the peak for azadirachtin D. Material from this peak yielded a new azadirachtin which was characterised by nmr spectroscopy as 3-tigloylmeliacarpin³⁸, crystals, m.p. 256°.

Through the use of direct preparative hplc ten azadirachtin analogues (including three already known) have been isolated in our laboratory. There are twenty other compounds of this group isolated in other laboratories by conventional separation procedures. All of the azadirachtins isolated by preparative hplc were solids, most of them crystalline. This cannot be said for most of the azadirachtins reported from other laboratories by column chromatography which were gums or liquids and poorly characterised except for nmr data.

It may be mentioned that from peaks 6-13 (Fig. 1) other

TABLE 1—AZADIRACTINS, AZADIRACTOLS AND MELIACARPINS ISOLATED FROM NATURAL SOURCES				Table-1 (contd.)			
Compd./ mol. formula	M.p./ Rotation	Biological activity*	Ref.				
Azadirachtin A (1), C ₃₅ H ₄₄ O ₁₆	174° [α] _D ²⁵ -71.4° (c = 0.21, CHCl ₃)	A EC ₅₀ 13 ppm, (F) G LC ₅₀ 1.66 ppm, (F) G 69% at 1 ppm, (T) G 60% at 0.01 μg	3,4,9-14, 26,27, 45-48	11-Demethoxy- carbonylazadirachtin (Azadirachtin H, 11β-H epimer) (13), C ₃₃ H ₄₂ O ₁₄	262-264° [α] _D ²³ -55.0° (c = 0.6, CHCl ₃)	-	14, 28-31, 33,34, 35
Azadirachtin C (2)	-	G EC ₅₀ 12.97 ppm	9,26	11-Acetyl-11- demethoxy- carbonylaza- dirachtin (Azadirachtin L, Marrangin) (14), C ₃₅ H ₄₄ O ₁₆	143-145°	G EC ₅₀ 0.25 ppm, L 100% at 1 ppm	54,55
1-Detigloylaza- dirachtin (Azadirachtin E) (3) C ₃₀ H ₃₈ O ₁₅	-	G EC ₅₀ 0.57 ppm	9,26	1-Detigloyl-3- deacetyl-3-tigloyl- azadirachtin (15), C ₃₃ H ₄₂ O ₁₅	160-162°	-	56
3-Deacetylaza- dirachtin (4), C ₃₃ H ₄₂ O ₁₅	-	G EC ₅₀ 0.38 ppm	9,26,27, 48,49	1-Detigloyl-3- deacetyl-3-tigloyl- deoxa-azadirachtin (Azadirachtin F) (16), C ₃₃ H ₄₄ O ₁₄	-	G EC ₅₀ 1.15 ppm	9
1-Dihydrodigloyl- azadirachtin (5), C ₃₅ H ₄₆ O ₁₆	-	-	49	11-Dehydroxy-11- oxo-azadirachtin-11, 12-lactone (Azadirachtin K) (17), C ₃₄ H ₄₀ O ₁₅	260°	-	36
3-Deacetyl-3- cinnamoylaza- dirachtin (6), C ₄₂ H ₄₈ O ₁₆	-	-	18	13,14-Desepoxy- azadirachtin A (18), C ₃₅ H ₄₄ O ₁₅	187° [α] _D ²³ +13.64° (c = 0.44, CHCl ₃)	-	37
1-Detigloyl-1- isobutyroylaza- dirachtin (7), C ₃₄ H ₄₄ O ₁₆	-	-	27,48-50	3-Tigloylazadirachtol (Azadirachtin B) (19), C ₃₃ H ₄₂ O ₁₄	204° [α] _D ²⁰ -69° (c = 0.1, CHCl ₃)	G EC ₅₀ 1.30 ppm, (T) G 70% at 0.01 μg, (F) G 85% at 2 ppm	9,22, 23,24, 26,27, 48,58
1-Detigloyl-1- isovaleroyl- azadirachtin (8), C ₃₅ H ₄₆ O ₁₆	-	A 100% at 100 ppm	27,48-50	2',3'-Dihydrodigloyl- azadirachtol (20), C ₃₃ H ₄₄ O ₁₄	-	FI 100% at 100 ppm	9,26, 27,48, 50
1-Detigloyl-1- isocaproyl-3- deacetyl-3-epoxy- methacroyl- azadirachtin (9), C ₃₈ H ₅₀ O ₁₇	-	-	27,48-50	3-Isobutyroyl- azadirachtol (21), C ₃₂ H ₄₂ O ₁₄	-	-	27,48, 50
22,23-Dihydro- 23β-methoxy- azadirachtin (vepaol) (10), C ₃₆ H ₄₈ O ₁₇	[α] _D ²⁰ -8.1° (c = 0.1, CHCl ₃)	(F) G 100% at 1 ppm, (T) G 70% at 100 ppm	18,51-53	3-Tigloyl-13,14- desepoxy-17- hydroxyazadirachtol (Azadirachtin G) (22), C ₃₂ H ₄₂ O ₁₄	-	G EC ₅₀ 7.69 ppm	9,26
22,23-Dihydro- 23α-methoxy- azadirachtin (isovepaol) (11), C ₃₆ H ₄₈ O ₁₇	-	-	53	1-Tigloyl-3-acetyl- azadirachtol (23), C ₃₅ H ₄₄ O ₁₅	-	-	8
11-Demethoxy- carbonyl- azadirachtin (Azadirachtin H, 11α-H epimer) (12), C ₃₃ H ₄₂ O ₁₄	248° [α] _D ²³ -33.3° (c = 0.6, CHCl ₃)	-	14, 28-31, 34,35	3α-Acetoxy-1α- hydroxy- azadirachtol (24), C ₃₀ H ₃₈ O ₁₄	132-135°	-	39
				Azadirachtol (25), C ₂₈ H ₃₆ O ₁₃	204° [α] _D ²⁰ -103.3° (c = 0.3, CHCl ₃)	-	9,26, 38,40

Table-1 (contd.)

1-Tigloyl-3-acetyl-11-hydroxy-meliacarpin (Azadirachtin D) (26), C ₃₄ H ₄₄ O ₁₄	196°	G EC ₅₀ 1.57 ppm, A 87% at 100 ppm	9,26, 27,50
1-Tigloyl-3-acetyl-11-hydroxy-11-demethoxycarbonylmeliacarpin (Azadirachtin I) (27), C ₃₂ H ₄₂ O ₁₂	192° [α] _D ²⁵ -21.8° (c = 0.8, CHCl ₃)	-	14,31
11-Demethoxycarbonyl-11-oxomeliacarpin (28), C ₃₂ H ₄₀ O ₁₂	-	-	28,50
1,3-Diacetyl-11,19-deoxa-11-oxo-meliacarpin (29), C ₃₁ H ₄₀ O ₁₃	-	-	57
3-Tigloylmeliacarpin (30) (new Azadirachtin), C ₃₂ H ₄₂ O ₁₂	256°	-	38

*Against *Epilachna varivestis*,

A = antifeedant activity, EC = effective concentration, (F) = application by feeding, G = growth inhibition, L = larvicidal activity, (T) = topical application, FI = feeding inhibition.

triterpenoids of neem such as nimbolide, ochinolide, desacetylsalannin, desacetylnimbin, azadiradione, nimbin, salannin and epoxyazadiradione were isolated by workup of various peaks. This is the first report of isolation of all principal triterpenoids from neem kernels. Similar results were obtained from the total triterpenoids from neem oil^{41,42}. From 1 kg of neem kernels 960 mg of azadirachtin, 330 mg of 3-tigloylazadirachtol, 126 mg of 1-tigloyl-3-acetyl-11-hydroxymeliacarpin, 60 mg of 11-demethoxycarbonylazadirachtin, 18 mg of 1-tigloyl-3-acetyl-11-hydroxy-11-demethoxycarbonylmeliacarpin and 3 mg of 11-dehydroxy-11-oxo-azadirachtin-11,12-lactone were obtained.

Biological activity :

In a comparative study of the antifeedant and growth regulatory activities of azadirachtins A, B, D, H and I and several tetranortriterpenoids of the limonoid class, it was shown that the former display a much higher degree of activity against *Spodoptera litura*. The only compound approaching azadirachtin in antifeedant and growth regulatory activity is salannin^{43,44}.

In Table 1, all the azadirachtins have been listed with physical data and their biological activity against *Epilachna varivestis* wherever available.

References

- S. PRADHAN, M. G. JOTWANI and B. K. RAI, *Indian Farming*, 1962, 12, 7.
- N. P. SINHA and K. C. GULATI, *Bull. Reg. Res. Lab., Jammu*, 1963, 1, 176.

- J. H. BUTTERWORTH and E. D. MORGAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1968, 23.
- J. H. BUTTERWORTH and E. D. MORGAN, *J. Insect Physiol.*, 1971, 17, 969.
- T. R. GOVINDACHARI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1992, 63, 117.
- S. SIDDIQUI, B. S. SIDDIQUI, S. FAIZI and I. MAHMOOD, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1988, 51, 30.
- C. DEVAKUMAR and SUKH DEV, 'Chemistry' in "Neem Research and Development", eds. N. S. RANDHAWA and B. S. PARMAR, Society of Pesticide Science, New Delhi, 1993, pp. 63-96.
- "The Neem tree *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. and other Meliaceae Plants", ed. H. SCHMUTTERER, VCH Verlagsgesellschaft, Weinheim, 1995, pp. 58-68.
- H. REMBOLD in "Focus on Phytochemical Pesticides", ed. M. JACOBSON, CRC Press Inc., Florida, 1989, pp. 47-86.
- E. C. UEBEL, J. D. WARTHEN, JR. and M. JACOBSON, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1979, 2, 875.
- R. B. YAMASAKI, J. A. KLOCKE, S. M. LEE, G. A. STONE and M. V. DARLINGTON, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1986, 356, 220.
- D. R. SCHROEDER and K. NAKANISHI, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1987, 50, 241.
- T. R. GOVINDACHARI, G. SANDHYA and S. P. GANESHRAJ, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1990, 513, 389.
- T. R. GOVINDACHARI, G. SANDHYA and S. P. GANESHRAJ, *Chromatographia*, 1991, 31, 303.
- D. A. H. TAYLOR, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, 43, 2779.
- C. J. TURNER, M. S. TEMPESTA, R. B. TAYLOR, M. G. ZAGORSKI, J. S. TERMINI, D. R. SCHROEDER and K. NAKANISHI, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, 43, 2789.
- J. N. BILTON, H. B. BROUGHTON, P. S. JONES, S. V. LEY, A. LIDERT, E. D. MORGAN, H. Z. RZEPA, R. N. SHEPPARD, A. M. Z. SLAWIN and D. J. WILLIAMS, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, 43, 2805.
- W. KRAUS, M. BOKEL A. BRUHN, R. CRAMER, I. KLAIBER, A. KLENK, G. NAGI, H. POHNL, H. SADLO and B. VOGLER, *Tetrahedron*, 1987, 43, 2817.
- H. B. BROUGHTON, S. V. LEY, A. M. Z. SLAWIN, D. J. WILLIAMS and E. D. MORGAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1986, 46.
- T. R. GOVINDACHARI, G. GOPALAKRISHNAN, R. RAGHUNATHAN and S. S. RAJAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1994, 66, 295.
- V. KABALEEWARAN, S. S. RAJAN, T. R. GOVINDACHARI and G. GOPALAKRISHNAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1994, 66, 362.
- A. KLENK, M. BOKEL and W. KRAUS, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1986, 523.
- H. REMBOLD, H. FORSTER and CH. CZOPPELT, 'Structure and biological activity of azadirachtins A and B' in 'Natural Pesticides from the Neem Tree and Other Tropical Plants', eds. H. SCHMUTTERER and K. R. S. ASCHER, (Proc. 3rd. Int. Neem Conf., Nairobi, 1986), pp. 149-160.
- H. REMBOLD, H. FORSTER and SONNENBICHLER, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil C*, 1987, 42, 4.
- T. R. GOVINDACHARI, G. GOPALAKRISHNAN and G. SURESH, *J. Liq. Chrom. Rel. Technol.*, 1997, 20, 1633.
- H. REMBOLD, 'Azadirachtins, their structure and mode of action' in "Insecticides of Plant Origin", eds. J. T. ARNASON, B. J.

- R. PHILOGENE and P. MORAND, ACS Symp. Ser. 387, American Chemical Society, Washington, DC, 1989, pp. 150-163.
27. W. KRAUS, S. BAUMANN, M. BOKEL, A. BRUHN, R. CRAMER, B. EHHAMMER, H. GUTZEIT, B. HERR, I. KAUFMANN-HORLACHER, U. KEELER, M. KILNGELE, M. SCHWINGER, S. THIELE, B. VOGLER, Y. ZHOU, R. SOELLNER, D. WENDISCH, R. STEFFENS and U. WACHENDORFF, 'Constituents of neem and other Meliaceae species in pest control' in "Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) for pest control and rural development in Asia and the Pacific", ed. S. AHMED, (17th Pacific Science Congress, Honolulu), 1991.
 28. S. R. ROJATKAR and B. A. NAGASAMPAGI, *Phytochemistry*, 1993, **32**, 213.
 29. B. A. NAGASAMPAGI, S. R. ROJATKAR, M. M. KULKARNI, C. D. BASARKAR and N. R. AYYANGAR, 17th IUPAC Symposium Abstracts, 1990, p. 88.
 30. S. R. ROJATKAR and B. A. NAGASAMPAGI, *Nat. Prod. Lett.*, 1994, **5**, 69.
 31. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, G. SANDHYA and S. P. GANESHRAJ, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1992, **55**, 596.
 32. T. R. GOVINDACHARI and G. GOPALAKRISHNAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1995, **68**, 31.
 33. N. RAMJI, K. VENKATAKRISHNAN and K. M. MADYASTHA, *Phytochemistry*, 1996, **42**, 561.
 34. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, G. GOPALAKRISHNAN, R. MALATHI and N. D. PRADEEP SINGH, communicated.
 35. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, G. GOPALAKRISHNAN, S. S. RAJAN and L. LESSINGER, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1996, **B52**, 145.
 36. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, G. SANDHYA and S. P. GANESHRAJ, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1992, **31**, 295.
 37. T. R. GOVINDACHARI and G. GOPALAKRISHNAN, *Phytochemistry*, 1997, **45**, 397.
 38. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, G. GOPALAKRISHNAN, R. MALATHI and S. S. RAJAN, unpublished results.
 39. S. R. ROJATKAR and B. A. NAGASAMPAGI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1995, **34**, 1016.
 40. S. V. LEY, A. A. DENHOLM and A. WOOD, *Nat. Prod. Rep.*, 1993, **10**, 109.
 41. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, G. SURESH and G. GOPALAKRISHNAN, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1995, **18**, 3465.
 42. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, G. GOPALAKRISHNAN and G. SURESH, *J. Liq. Chrom. Rel. Technol.*, 1996, **19**, 1729.
 43. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, N. S. NARASIMHAN, G. SURESH, P. D. PARTHO, G. GOPALAKRISHNAN and G. N. KRISHNAKUMARI, *J. Chem. Ecol.*, 1995, **21**, 1585.
 44. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, N. S. NARASIMHAN, G. SURESH, P. D. PARTHO and G. GOPALAKRISHNAN, *J. Chem. Ecol.*, 1996, **22**, 1453.
 45. W. KRAUS, M. BOKEL, A. KLENK and H. POHNL, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1985, **26**, 6435.
 46. W. KRAUS, *Stud. Org. Chem.*, 1986, **26**, 237.
 47. M. SCHWINGER, B. EHHAMMER and W. KRAUS, 'Methodology of the *Epilachna varivestis* bioassay of antifeedants demonstrated with some compounds from *Azadirachta indica* and *Melia azadirach* in "Natural Pesticides from the Neem Tree and other Tropical Plants", eds. H. SCHMUTTERER and K. R. S. ASCHER, Proc. 2nd. Int. Neem Conf. (Rauischholzhausen, Germany, 1983), 1984, pp. 181-198.
 48. W. KRAUS, M. BOKEL, M. SCHWINGER, B. VOGLER, R. SOELLNER, D. WENDISCH, R. STEFFENS and U. WACHENDORFF, 'The chemistry of azadirachtin and other insecticidal constituents of meliaceae' in "Phytochemistry and Agriculture", eds. T. VAN BEEK and H. BRETELER, Oxford University Press, 1993, pp. 18-39.
 49. S. THIELE, 'Isolierung und Strukturaufklärung neuer Tetrano-triterpenoide aus *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss (neem tree, Meliaceae) and Untersuchung der nematiziden Wirkung von Neem Extrakten', Doctor. Thesis, University of Hohenheim, Germany, 1991.
 50. Y. ZHOU-HALWART, 'Isolierung und Strukturaufklärung neuer Tetranortriterpenoide aus *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss (Meliaceae, Neem-Baum) mit insektenfraßhemmender Wirkung', Doctor Thesis, University of Hohenheim, Verlag Koster, Berlin, 1993.
 51. W. KRAUS, M. BOKEL, R. CRAMER, A. KLENK and H. POHNL, 'Constituents of neem and related species. A revised structure of azadirachtin', Third Int. Conf on Chemistry and Biotechnology of Biologically Active Natural Products (Sofia, Bulgaria) 1985, Abstr., pp. 446-450.
 52. W. KRAUS, M. BOKEL, A. KLENK and H. POHNL, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1985, **26**, 6435.
 53. A. V. B. SANKARAM, M. M. MURTHY, K. BHASKARAIHAH, M. SUBAMANYAM, N. SULTANA, H. C. SHARMA, K. LEUSCHNER, G. RAMAPRASAD, S. SITARAMAIAH, C. RUKMINI and P. U. RAO, 'Chemistry, biological activity and utilization aspects of some promising neem extractives', in Ref. 23, 1987, pp. 127-148.
 54. K. ERMEL, H. O. KALINOWSKI and H. SCHMUTTERER, *J. Appl. Entomol.*, 1991, **112**, 512.
 55. H. O. KALINOWSKI, K. ERMEL and H. SCHMUTTERER, *Justus Liebig's Ann. Chem.*, 1993, 1033.
 56. C. S. S. R. KUMAR, M. SRINIVAS and S. YAKKUNDI, *Phytochemistry*, 1996, **43**, 451.
 57. W. KRAUS, H. GUTZEIT and M. BOKEL, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1989, **30**, 1797.
 58. J. N. BILTON, P. S. JONES, S. V. LEY, N. G. ROBINSON and R. N. SHEPPARD, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1988, **29**, 1849.